

1 **Rb-dependent and Rb-independent CDK4/6 transcriptional targets in transformed settings.**

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6 We describe here a subset of genes whose expression is regulated by CDK4/6 following in vitro exposure
7 of cells to the CDK4/6 inhibitor palbociclib: CDK4/6-regulated genes whose expression is dependent on or
8 independent of *Rb1*. Deletion of *Rb1* in transformed T cells *in vitro* resulted in activation of an immune
9 program including *NLRC3*, granzyme A, *CD38*, *HLA-E* and *CD1e*. While MKI67 reduction was unaffected,
10 reduction in PCNA expression was compromised in *Rb1* KO cells, indicating alterations in proliferation
11 dynamics. Polymerase silencing was affected, including failure to regulate expression of RNA polymerase
12 *POLR2J4* in the absence of *Rb1*. *PIK3R1* was transcriptionally inactive in *Rb*-sufficient cells, whereas it
13 was a top activated gene in *Rb1* KO cells exposed to a CDK4/6 inhibitor. *Rb1*-deficient cells failed to
14 activate CFLAR in response to CDK4/6 inhibition. In *Rb1* KO breast cancer cells, E2F inactivation was
15 partially compromised, and proliferation defects in response to CDK4/6 inhibition were more apparent, with
16 complete loss of MKI67 reduction. Importantly, strict repression of cell cycle target genes observed in *Rb1*
17 sufficient breast cancer cells, like that of G2 and S-phase expressed 1 (*GTSE1*, DNA polymerase E
18 (*POLE*) and DNA polymerase E2 (*POLE2*) was lost. While palbociclib was effective in reducing ECT2
19 expression, demonstrating effectiveness of the CDK4/6 inhibitor as a senescence inducing agent in
20 transformation inhibition, ECT2 reduction was completely lost in *Rb1*-deficient breast cancer cells. *Rb1*
21 status impacts coordination of cycling and replication of the daughter strand, genes that regulate cell
22 death, energy homeostasis, and immune activation status.
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